

An Inverse Branchweight Centroid Problem on Some Graphs

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Abstract

Given a graph G with a positive weight for each vertex in G , the branchweight centroid problem on G is to find a vertex in G with the minimum branchweight where the branchweight of a vertex means the maximum of the weights of its branches. In this paper we first introduce an inverse branchweight centroid problem on a tree T whose objective is to change the weights of the given tree T at minimum cost so that a specified vertex in T becomes the branchweight centroid of T with respect to the new vertex weights. Then we give a mathematical formulation of this problem and suggest an efficient algorithm for it.

Key words: branchweight of a vertex, branchweight centroids of a tree, inverse branchweight centroid of a tree

Introduction

Given a real world transportation or communication network, we often need to find positions in the network at which one or more facilities should be installed in such a way that some kinds of service to be given by these facilities would be optimal with respect to some criteria. Such an optimization problem is known as an *optimal location problem* and several types of these optimal location problems have been extensively studied in the literature. A reverse situation which often arises in practice is as follows.

We are given a real world network in which one or more servicing facilities have been already installed at certain locations of the network. The problem is to change some parameters of the network at minimum cost so that the service given by those facilities is optimal. Such a problem is known as an *optimal inverse location problem*. Various types of optimal inverse location problems have also been studied in the literature.

In this paper we shall deal with the inverse branchweight centroid problem on a tree and present an efficient method for solving it. In the first section, we define the branchweight centroid problem on a tree and some theoretical results on that problem. Then, we formulate the inverse branchweight centroid problem on a tree, and finally we develop an efficient method for solving this problem in last section.

The Branchweight Centroid Problem on a Tree

Throughout this paper we shall consider a tree T with the vertex set $V(T)$, the edge set $E(T)$ and a positive weight $w(v)$ for each vertex $v \in V(T)$.

Definitions. Let T be a tree with a positive weight $w(u)$ for each vertex u in T . Suppose that for a vertex $v \in V(T)$ $T - v$, the graph obtained from T by deleting the vertex v consists of k components T_1, T_2, \dots, T_k which are subtrees of T . For each i with $1 \leq i \leq k$, we call T_i a *branch* of v . We denote the *branchweight* of v with respect to the vertex weights w by $b(v)$ or $b_w(v)$ if necessary and it is defined as

$$b(v) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq k} \left(\sum_{v \in V(T_i)} w(v) \right).$$

For any subgraph H of T , we denote the *weight* of H by $w(H)$ and define it as

$$w(H) = \sum_{v \in V(H)} w(v).$$

Thus the branchweight $b(v)$ of the vertex v in T is

$$b(v) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq k} w(T_i),$$

and hence the branchweight $b(v)$ of v is the maximum of the weights of its branches.

A vertex v^* in T is call a **branchweight centroid** of T if

$$b(v^*) \leq b(v)$$

for every vertex v in T , i.e., if v^* has the minimum branchweight.

The Branchweight Centroid Problem on a Tree. Given a tree T with a positive weight $w(u)$ for each vertex u in T , the **branchweight centroid problem** (BCP) on T is to find a branchweight centroid of T .

Example. Consider the tree T shown in Figure 1 with a positive weight at each vertex in T .

Figure 1

If we delete the vertex o from T , we obtain the graph $T - o$ with three components T_1, T_2 and T_3 shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2

We can find that

$$w(T_1) = 11, w(T_2) = 14, \text{ and } w(T_3) = 15.$$

So the branchweight $b(o)$ of o is

$$\begin{aligned} b(o) &= \max \{w(T_1), w(T_2), w(T_3)\} \\ &= \max \{11, 14, 15\} \\ &= 15. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly we can find that

$$b(l) = 40, b(m) = 39, b(n) = 32, b(o) = 15, b(p) = 29, b(q) = 39, b(r) = 42, \\ b(s) = 39, b(t) = 41, b(u) = 28, b(w) = 40, b(x) = 42, b(y) = 35, b(z) = 40,$$

and it follows that

$$b(o) \leq b(v)$$

for every vertex v in T . So o is the branchweight centroid of T .

The following characterizations of the branchweight centroids of a tree are important from both theoretical and computational points of view. For the proofs of these results, one may see Myint [5].

Theorem. Let T be a tree with a positive weight $w(v)$ for each vertex v in T . A vertex x in T is a branchweight centroid of T if and only if

$$w(T_{(x,y)}) \geq w(T_{(y,x)})$$

for every vertex y in T adjacent to x .

Here $T_{(x,y)}$ (resp. $T_{(y,x)}$) denotes the component of $T - xy$ containing the vertex x (resp. y).

Corollary. Let T be a tree with a positive weight $w(v)$ for each vertex v in T . A vertex x in T is a branchweight centroid of T if and only if

$$w(T_{(x,y)}) \geq \frac{1}{2} w(T)$$

for every vertex y adjacent to x .

Corollary. Let T be a tree with a positive weight $w(v)$ for each vertex v in T . A vertex x in T is a unique branchweight centroid of T if and only if

$$w(T_{(x,y)}) > w(T_{(y,x)}),$$

equivalently

$$w(T_{(x,y)}) > \frac{1}{2} w(T)$$

for every vertex y adjacent to x .

Corollary. Let T be a tree with a positive weight $w(v)$ for each vertex v in T and let x, y be two adjacent vertices in T . Then both x and y are branchweight centroids of T if and only if

$$w(T_{(x,y)}) = w(T_{(y,x)}) = \frac{1}{2} w(T).$$

Corollary. Let T be a tree with a positive weight $w(v)$ for each vertex v in T . Then the set of branchweight centroids of T consists of only one vertex or two adjacent vertices.

These theoretical results are found to be useful in developing efficient solution strategies for finding the branchweight centroids of a given tree; see, for instance, Myint.

We will see in the next section that these results are also helpful in designing an efficient algorithm for the inverse branchweight centroid problem on a tree.

An Inverse Branchweight Centroid Problem on a Tree

In this section we shall introduce an inverse branchweight centroid problem on a tree. Roughly speaking, given a tree T with a positive weight for each vertex in T and a specified vertex v_0 of T , the problem is to change the weights of the vertices of T in such a way that v_0 becomes the branchweight centroid of T with respect to new vertex weights and the total cost of changing the weights of the vertices of T is minimum. A more precise description of the problem can be given as follows.

Statement of the Problem. Let T be a tree with the vertex set $V(T)$, the edge set $E(T)$ and a positive weight $w(v)$ for each vertex v in T . Suppose that for each vertex v in T , there exist two nonnegative numbers $i(v)$ and $d(v)$ where $i(v)$ (resp. $d(v)$) represents the maximum amount by which the weight $w(v)$ of the vertex v can be increased (resp. decreased). Suppose also that for each vertex v in T there exist two positive costs $c^+(v)$ and $c^-(v)$ where $c^+(v)$ (resp. $c^-(v)$) is the cost of increasing (resp. decreasing) the weight $w(v)$ of the vertex v by one unit. Furthermore, suppose that a specified vertex v_0 in T be given. The **inverse branchweight centroid problem** (IBCP) on T is to change (i.e., increase or decrease) the weights $w(v)$ of the vertices v in T , if necessary, in such a way that the upper bound constraints for changing the weights of the vertices are satisfied, the specified vertex v_0 becomes the branchweight centroid of T with respect to the new vertex weights and the total cost of changing the vertex weights of T is minimum.

Formulation of the Problem. To give a mathematical formulation of the IBCP on the tree T stated above, we consider, for each vertex v in T , two variables $x^+(v)$ and $x^-(v)$ where $x^+(v)$ (resp. $x^-(v)$) represents the amount by which the weight $w(v)$ of the vertex v is increased (resp. decreased). Obviously $x^+(v)$ and $x^-(v)$ must satisfy the following conditions:

$$0 \leq x^+(v) \leq i(v),$$

$$0 \leq x^-(v) \leq d(v).$$

If the weight $w(v)$ of a vertex v is increased by $x^+(v)$ units and decreased by $x^-(v)$ units, then the new weight $w'(v)$ of the vertex v will be as follows:

$$w'(v) = w(v) + x^+(v) - x^-(v).$$

Since the specified vertex v_0 is to be the branchweight centroid of T with respect to the new weights $w'(v)$, we must have

$$b_{w'}(v_0) \leq b_{w'}(v) \text{ for every vertex } v \in V(T).$$

The cost of increasing the weight of the vertex v by $x^+(v)$ units is $c^+(v) x^+(v)$ and that of decreasing it by $x^-(v)$ units is $c^-(v) x^-(v)$. Therefore the total cost of changing the weights of all the vertices in T is

$$\sum_{v \in V(T)} (c^+(v)x^+(v) + c^-(v)x^-(v)).$$

Since the costs $c^+(v)$ and $c^-(v)$ of increasing and decreasing the weight $w(v)$ of the vertex v by one unit respectively are positive, $x^+(v)$ and $x^-(v)$ cannot be both positive in an optimal solution. Thus we can assume without loss of generality that $x^+(v)$ and $x^-(v)$ satisfy the following condition:

$$x^+(v) x^-(v) = 0 \text{ for every vertex } v \in V(T).$$

By compiling these discussion we can now give a formulation of the IBCP on T as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \min & \quad \sum_{v \in V(T)} (c^+(v)x^+(v) + c^-(v)x^-(v)) \\ \text{subject to} & \quad w'(v) = w(v) + x^+(v) - x^-(v) \quad \text{for every vertex } v \in V(T), \\ & \quad b_{w'}(v_0) \leq b_w(v) \quad \text{for every vertex } v \in V(T), \\ & \quad 0 \leq x^+(v) \leq i(v) \quad \text{for every vertex } v \in V(T), \\ & \quad 0 \leq x^-(v) \leq d(v) \quad \text{for every vertex } v \in V(T), \\ & \quad x^+(v)x^-(v) = 0 \quad \text{for every vertex } v \in V(T). \end{aligned}$$

Example. Consider the weighted tree T shown in Figure 3 with the vertex set $V(T) = \{l, m, n, o, p, q, r, s, t, u\}$.

Figure 3

For all vertices in $V(T)$, the parameters $i(v), d(v), c^+(v)$ and $c^-(v)$ are given by Table 1.

Table 1

v	$i(v)$	$d(v)$	$c^+(v)$	$c^-(v)$
l	2	2	3	2
m	2	1	2	2
n	3	1	2	1
o	2	1	1	1
p	2	2	3	2
q	1	1	2	2
r	1	2	1	1
s	1	1	1	2
t	1	1	4	2
u	2	2	1	1

Let $v_0 = q$ be the specified vertex in T . Then the IBCP on T with these parameters can

be stated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min \quad & (3x^+(l) + 2x^-(l)) + (2x^+(m) + 2x^-(m)) + (2x^+(n) + 1x^-(n)) \\
 & + (1x^+(o) + 1x^-(o)) + (3x^+(p) + 2x^-(p)) + (2x^+(q) + 2x^-(q)) \\
 & + (1x^+(r) + 1x^-(r)) + (1x^+(s) + 2x^-(s)) + (4x^+(t) + 2x^-(t)) \\
 & + (1x^+(u) + 1x^-(u)) \\
 \text{subject to} \quad & w'(l) = 2 + x^+(v) - x^-(v), w'(m) = 2 + x^+(v) - x^-(v), \\
 & w'(n) = 3 + x^+(v) - x^-(v), w'(o) = 5 + x^+(v) - x^-(v), \\
 & w'(p) = 3 + x^+(v) - x^-(v), w'(q) = 4 + x^+(v) - x^-(v), \\
 & w'(r) = 4 + x^+(v) - x^-(v), w'(s) = 2 + x^+(v) - x^-(v), \\
 & w'(t) = 6 + x^+(v) - x^-(v), w'(u) = 2 + x^+(v) - x^-(v), \\
 & b_w(q) \leq b_w(v) \quad \text{for every vertex } v \in V(T), \\
 \\
 & 0 \leq x^+(l) \leq 2, 0 \leq x^-(l) \leq 2, 0 \leq x^+(m) \leq 2, 0 \leq x^-(m) \leq 1, \\
 & 0 \leq x^+(n) \leq 3, 0 \leq x^-(n) \leq 1, 0 \leq x^+(o) \leq 2, 0 \leq x^-(o) \leq 1, \\
 & 0 \leq x^+(p) \leq 2, 0 \leq x^-(p) \leq 2, 0 \leq x^+(q) \leq 1, 0 \leq x^-(q) \leq 1, \\
 & 0 \leq x^+(r) \leq 1, 0 \leq x^-(r) \leq 2, 0 \leq x^+(s) \leq 1, 0 \leq x^-(s) \leq 1, \\
 & 0 \leq x^+(t) \leq 1, 0 \leq x^-(t) \leq 1, 0 \leq x^+(u) \leq 2, 0 \leq x^-(u) \leq 2, \\
 & x^+(v)x^-(v) = 0 \quad \text{for every vertex } v \in V(T).
 \end{aligned}$$

An Algorithm for Solving the Inverse Branchweight Centroid Problem on a Tree

By using the properties of the branchweight centroid of a tree stated in Section 2, we now develop an efficient algorithm for solving the IBCP on a tree T .

An Outline of the Algorithm. Using the depth-first search process, we compute the weights of each branch of the specified vertex v_0 . If the weight of each branch of v_0 is no more than $\frac{1}{2}w(T)$, then by Theorem 2.4, it is true that v_0 is already the branchweight centroid of T with respect to the given vertex weights $w(v)$ and so we do not need to change the weights of the vertices of T . Otherwise we have a branch T' of the vertex v_0 such that $w(T') > \frac{1}{2}w(T)$. In this case we optimally decrease the weights of the vertices in T' and increase the weights of the vertices not in T' , and this can be done by solving an associated knapsack problem.

A Detailed Description of the Algorithm. (A detailed description of the algorithm can be given as follows.)

Input: a tree T with the vertex set $V(T)$ and the edge set $E(T)$, a positive weight $w(v)$ for each vertex v in T , a specified vertex v_0 in T , two nonnegative numbers $i(v)$ and $d(v)$ for each vertex v in T which are the maximum amounts by which the weight $w(v)$ of the vertex v can be increased and decreased respectively and two positive numbers

$c^+(v)$ and $c^-(v)$ for each vertex v in T which are the costs of increasing and decreasing the weight of v by one unit respectively.

Output: a weight $w'(v)$ for each vertex v in T giving the optimal solution of the IBCP on T .

Initializations

Step 1. For each vertex $v \in V(T)$, initialize its accumulated weight $aw(v)$ with its weight $w(v)$, define a logical variable $visit(v)$ and initialize $visit(v) := \text{false}$.

Compute the weight $w(T)$ of the given tree T which is the sum of the weights of all vertices in T and set $K := \frac{1}{2}w(T)$.

For each vertex v in T ,

set $N(v_0) :=$ the set of all neighbors of v_0 , i.e., the set of all vertices adjacent to v_0 .

Choosing a Vertex in $N(v_0)$

Step 2. If $N(v_0) = \emptyset$, output the information that we do not need to change the vertex weights of T , i.e., v_0 is already a branchweight centroid of the given tree T , and stop. Otherwise choose a vertex $u \in N(v_0)$.

Performing a Depth-First Search Process in $T_{(u,v_0)}$, the Branch of v_0 Containing u

Step 3. Set $S := \emptyset$ where S stores the set of vertices already visited by the depth-first search process which will be done below,

$root := u$ where $root$ represents the vertex at which the depth-first search process starts,

$c := u$ where c represents the vertex which is currently scanned by the depth-first search process,

$visit(c) := \text{true}$,

$S := S \cup \{c\}$.

Step 4. Choose a vertex y in $V(T) \setminus \{v_0\}$ such that y is adjacent to c and $visit(y) = \text{false}$. If such a vertex y does not exist, go to Step 6.

Step 5. Set $p(y) := c$ where $p(y)$ represents the parent vertex of y ,

$c := y$,

$visit(c) := \text{true}$,

$S := S \cup \{c\}$.

Go to Step 4.

Step 6. (i) If $c = root$ and $aw(c) = K$, then output the information that we do not need to

change the vertex weights of T , i.e., v_0 is already a branchweight centroid of the given weighted tree T , and stop.

(ii) If $c = \text{root}$ and $aw(c) > K$, then go to Step 8.

(iii) If $c = \text{root}$ and $aw(c) < K$, then set $N(v_0) := N(v_0) \setminus \{\text{root}\}$ and go to Step 2.

(iv) If $c \neq \text{root}$, then go to Step 7.

Step 7. Set $aw(p(c)) := aw(p(c)) + aw(c)$,

$$c := p(c).$$

Go to Step 4.

Constructing and Solving a Knapsack Problem

Step 8. Solve the problem

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \sum_{v \notin S} c^+(v)x^+(v) + \sum_{v \in S} c^-(v)x^-(v) \\ \text{subject to} \quad & w(T) - aw(c) + \sum_{v \notin S} x^+(v) = aw(c) - \sum_{v \in S} x^-(v), \\ & 0 \leq x^+(v) \leq i(v) \quad \text{for every vertex } v \notin S, \\ & 0 \leq x^-(v) \leq d(v) \quad \text{for every vertex } v \in S, \end{aligned}$$

which is equivalent to the knapsack problem

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \sum_{v \notin S} c^+(v)x^+(v) + \sum_{v \in S} c^-(v)x^-(v) \\ \text{subject to} \quad & \sum_{v \notin S} x^+(v) + \sum_{v \in S} x^-(v) = 2aw(c) - w(T), \\ & 0 \leq x^+(v) \leq i(v) \quad \text{for every vertex } v \notin S, \\ & 0 \leq x^-(v) \leq d(v) \quad \text{for every vertex } v \in S. \end{aligned}$$

If this problem is found to be infeasible output the information that the given IBCP has no feasible solution and stop.

Step 9. Suppose that $\{x_*^+(v) \mid v \notin S\} \cup \{x_*^-(v) \mid v \in S\}$ constitutes an optimal solution of the knapsack problem in Step 8. Define the new weights

$$\begin{aligned} w'(v) &= w(v) + x_*^+(v) \quad \text{for every vertex } v \notin S, \\ w'(v) &= w(v) - x_*^-(v) \quad \text{for every vertex } v \in S, \end{aligned}$$

output these new weights $w'(v)$ for all vertices $v \in V(T)$ with respect to which the specified vertex v_0 is a branchweight centroid of T and stop.

The correctness of Algorithm 4.2 is guaranteed by the following theorem.

Theorem. Algorithm 4.2 correctly solves the IBCP on a given tree T in $O(n \log n)$ time

$$\text{where } n = |V(T)|.$$

Proof. The proof is divided into three cases.

Case 1. Suppose that the algorithm stops in Step 2. Then we can easily see from the design of

the algorithm that for every vertex u adjacent to v_0 ,

$$w(T_{(u,v_0)}) < \frac{1}{2} w(T),$$

equivalently

$$w(T_{(v_0,u)}) > w(T_{(u,v_0)}).$$

So, by Corollary 2.6, it is true that v_0 is already a branchweight centroid of T with respect to the given weights $w(v)$ and hence we do not need to change the vertex weights.

Case 2. Suppose that the algorithm stops in Step 6 (i). Then we can see from the design of the algorithm that for the currently scanned vertex c which is adjacent to v_0

$$w(T_{(c,v_0)}) = w(T_{(v_0,c)}) = \frac{1}{2} w(T).$$

So, by Corollary 2.7, it is true that both v_0 and c are the branchweight centroids of T with respect to the given vertex weights $w(v)$ and hence we do not need to change the vertex weights.

Case 3. Suppose that Case 1 and Case 2 do not hold. Then the execution of the algorithm reaches Step 6 (ii) and obtains a vertex u adjacent to v_0 such that

$$w(T_{(u,v_0)}) > \frac{1}{2} w(T)$$

and

$$S = V(T_{(u,v_0)}).$$

By Corollary 2.6, the specified vertex v_0 is not a branchweight centroid of T with respect to the original vertex weights and we have to change the vertex weights $w(v)$ at minimum cost so that v_0 becomes the branchweight centroid of T with respect to the new vertex weights if it is possible. By Corollary, this is equivalent to that of increasing the weights of the vertices in $V(T) \setminus S$ and decreasing the weights of the vertices in S subject to the given bounds $i(v)$ and $d(v)$ and at minimum total cost. It is not difficult to see that this is equivalent to solving the knapsack problem stated in Step 8. By Corollary, the infeasibility of the knapsack problem implies that of the given IBCP. On the other hand if an optimal solution of the knapsack problem exists, then it gives an optimal change of the vertex weights $w(v)$ under which the specified vertex v_0 becomes a branchweight centroid of T . This completes our proof.

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